

Achieving Prescribed Performance for Euler-Lagrange Systems with Impulsive Behaviour*

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Abstract—We consider the problem of controlling, with prescribed performance, uncertain Euler-Lagrange systems in the presence of aperiodic impulses affecting the system state. Between any two consecutive impulse time instants, we guarantee that the output tracking error converges to a predefined and arbitrarily small region of interest, within a prespecified fixed time. Furthermore, all signals in the closed-loop are bounded. The magnitude of the impulses and their time of appearance are unknown in advance. Yet a known minimum time interval is required to elapse, before the appearance of a new impulse. Simulation results clarify and verify the theoretical findings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Impulses may appear as a form of disturbances in nature. Within systems theory, impulsive systems combine both continuous and discontinuous dynamics, making their stability analysis challenging [1]. The presence of impulsive systems has been reported in reset systems [2], in network control systems (NCSs) [3], in mechanical systems [4], in robotics [5] and in industrial electronics [6]. In addition, impacts can be modeled as impulsive phenomena [7].

A large number of physical systems can be modeled by Euler-Lagrange equations. In that respect, closed-loop Euler-Lagrange systems with impulsive characteristics have received significant attention. For a class of underactuated systems, impulsive control achieved the enlargement of the region of attraction [8]. In [9] asymptotic stability is ensured in cases of impact with constrained surfaces. Stability issues for Euler-Lagrange multi-agent systems is examined in [10], [11]. In all aforementioned works the system dynamics are considered known in advance, a hypothesis that is rarely satisfied in real applications. Attempts to alleviate this issue are provided in [12], [13] utilizing neural networks. However, the use of approximation-based techniques introduces robustness issues that directly influence negatively the stability of the closed-loop. Moreover, the results are local, as initialization should be restricted to a compact subset of the set in which the universal approximation capabilities hold, without this subset being known in advance. Additionally, the complexity of the proposed control solution is significantly increased as extra adaptive parameters have to be updated (i.e., nonlinear differential equations have to be solved numerically) and extra calculations have to be conducted to produce the control signal, thus making implementation difficult.

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Furthermore, all stated works deal with the stability issue leaving the problem of performance overlooked. Proposing controllers capable of guaranteeing prescribed performance attributes in terms of maximum steady-state error, maximum overshoot, minimum convergence time etc., while preserving the complexity of the control solution at low levels, is of paramount importance. Valid solution in this direction is provided with the help of the prescribed performance control (PPC) methodology, pioneered in [14] for approximation-based schemes, and further developed in [15]–[22] proposing approximation-free controllers. Within PPC, the first approach that confronted impulsive behaviour is [23] with impulses appearing owing to discontinuities in the reference signal instead of the state variables.

Inspired by the PPC methodology, the objective of this work is to design a low-complexity, approximation free, and static controller for impulsive Euler-Lagrange systems having no knowledge regarding their actual nonlinearities. We consider impulses affecting the systems state. Both their magnitude and time of appearance are unknown in advance. Nevertheless, a known minimum time interval is required to elapse before the appearance of a new impulse. We guarantee that all signals in the closed-loop are bounded and the output tracking error converges to a neighborhood of zero of pre-selected magnitude in no greater than a predefined fixed time, between any two consecutive impulse time instants.

The article is organised as follows. In Section II we formulate the problem. We present the main results in Section III and their proof in Section IV. Simulations that clarify and verify our approach are illustrated in Section V. Finally, we conclude in Section VI.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider an Euler-Lagrange system of the form

$$M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + g(q) = u \quad (1)$$

where $q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are vectors of generalized positions, velocities and accelerations respectively, $M(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the symmetric positive definite inertia matrix, $C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the vector of Coriolis and centripetal torques, $g(q) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the potential force vector and $u \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the vector of external control inputs. Defining the state variables $x_1 = q$ and $x_2 = \dot{q}$ and introducing impulsive phenomena, system (1) takes the form:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= x_2, \\ \dot{x}_2 &= M^{-1}(x_1)(u - C(x_1, x_2)x_2 - g(x_1)) \end{aligned} \right\} t \notin \mathbb{J}, \quad (2)$$

$$x_i(t) = x_i(t^-) + \Delta x_i(k), \quad i = 1, 2, \quad t \in \mathbb{J}.$$

where $\mathbb{J} = \{t_k : k \in \mathbb{N}_+\}$, short for $\{t_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}_+}$ represents the set of impulse sequence.

Assumption 1: The desired trajectories $y_{d,j}(t) \in \mathbb{R}$, $j = 1, \dots, n$ and their first order derivative are continuous and bounded. However, $y_{d,j}(t)$ is known only at the current time instant and $\dot{y}_{d,i}$ are considered unknown.

Assumption 2: The impulses $\Delta x_1(k), \Delta x_2(k)$ are considered bounded. Furthermore, $t_{k+1} - t_k \geq \bar{\tau} > 0$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$, with $\bar{\tau}$ being a known constant. However, the impulse time instants are unknown in advance.

Control Objective: Consider the nonlinear impulsive system (2) satisfying Assumption 2. Moreover, consider the desired trajectories $y_{d,j}(t) \in \mathbb{R}$, $j = 1, \dots, n$ satisfying Assumption 1 and the corresponding output tracking errors $e_{1,j} = x_{1,j} - y_{d,j}$. Design an impulsive controller to guarantee that a) $|e_{1,j}(t)|$ will be strictly less than a predefined value $\delta_{1,j} > 0$ for all $j = 1, \dots, n$, and $t \in [t_k + \tau, t_{k+1})$, $\tau < \bar{\tau}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, where $\tau > 0$ is a predefined fixed time; b) all closed loop signals are bounded.

III. MAIN RESULTS

The following theorem, whose proof is presented in Section IV, summarize the main result of this work.

Theorem 1: Consider the impulsive Euler-Lagrange system (2) and Assumption 1. Let τ be a predefined time instant satisfying $\bar{\tau} > \tau > 0$ and $\delta_{1,j} > 0$ are given constants. Define $e_{1,j} = x_{1,j} - y_{d,j}$. Given any initial conditions $[x_1(t_0), x_2(t_0)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times n}$ and for all $j = 1, \dots, n$ the control law:

$$a_0 = y_d \in \mathbb{R}^n, \quad (3a)$$

$$\sigma_i = (\rho_i)^{-1}(x_i - a_{i-1}) \in \mathbb{R}^n, \quad i = 1, 2, \quad (3b)$$

$$a_i = -k_i s_i - k'_i \epsilon_i \in \mathbb{R}^n, \quad i = 1, 2, \quad (3c)$$

$$u = a_2 \in \mathbb{R}^n, \quad (3d)$$

where

$$\rho_i(t) = \text{diag}([\rho_{i,1}, \rho_{i,2}, \dots, \rho_{i,n}]) \quad (3e)$$

$$\rho_{i,j}(t) = (\rho_{i,j}^k - \rho_{i,j}^\infty) e^{-\lambda_{i,j}^k (t-t_k)} + \rho_{i,j}^\infty, \quad t \in [t_k, t_{k+1}), \quad (3f)$$

$$\rho_{i,j}(t) = \rho_{i,j}(t^-) + \Delta \rho_{i,j}(k), \quad t \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (3g)$$

$$\Delta \rho_i(k) = \beta_i |\Delta x_i(k)| I + \beta'_i |\Delta a_{i-1}(k)| I, \quad i = 1, 2, \quad t \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (3h)$$

$$\Delta a_i(k) = a_i(t) - a_i(t^-), \quad i = 0, 1, \quad t \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (3i)$$

$$s_i = [T^3(\sigma_{i,1}), \dots, T^3(\sigma_{i,n})]^T, \quad i = 1, 2, \quad (3j)$$

$$\epsilon_i = [T(\sigma_{i,1}), \dots, T(\sigma_{i,n})]^T, \quad i = 1, 2, \quad (3k)$$

$$k_i = \text{diag}([k_{i,1}, \dots, k_{i,n}]), \quad k'_i = \text{diag}([k'_{i,1}, \dots, k'_{i,n}]), \quad (3l)$$

$$\beta_i = \text{diag}([\beta_{i,1}, \dots, \beta_{i,n}]), \quad \beta'_i = \text{diag}([\beta'_{i,1}, \dots, \beta'_{i,n}]), \quad (3m)$$

$$|\Delta x_i(k)| = [|\Delta x_{i,1}(k)|, \dots, |\Delta x_{i,n}(k)|]^T, \quad (3n)$$

$$|\Delta a_i(k)| = [|\Delta a_{i,1}(k)|, \dots, |\Delta a_{i,n}(k)|]^T, \quad (3o)$$

with $\beta_{i,j}, \beta'_{i,j} > 1$, $k_{i,j}, k'_{i,j} > 0$, $T : (-1, 1) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $T(z) = \ln((1+z)/(1-z))$, where I is the $n \times n$ unity matrix and

$$\lambda_{i,j}^k > \ln\left(\frac{\rho_{i,j}^k - \rho_{i,j}^\infty}{\delta_{i,j} - \rho_{i,j}^\infty}\right) / \tau, \quad \rho_{i,j}^k \geq \rho_{i,j}^\infty > 0, \quad \rho_{i,j}^\infty < \delta_{i,j}, \quad (3p)$$

$$\rho_{i,j}^0 \equiv \rho_{i,j}(0) > |x_{i,j} - a_{i-1,j}|, \quad \rho_{i,j}^k = \rho_{i,j}(t_k), \quad i = 1, 2, \quad (3q)$$

guarantees:

- 1) the boundedness of all signals in the closed loop;
- 2) $|e_{1,j}(t)| < \delta_{1,j}, \forall t \in [t_k + \tau, t_{k+1})$.

Remark 1: The proposed controller (3) is static. It does not require a priori knowledge of the actual system nonlinearities, and no approximating structures i.e., fuzzy systems or neural networks are utilized to acquire such knowledge. Finally, no hard calculations (analytic or numerical) are required. Therefore, it presents low complexity characteristics.

IV. PROOF OF THEOREM 1

Differentiating (3b) with respect to time, it yields

$$\dot{\sigma}_1 = (\rho_1)^{-1}(\rho_2 \sigma_2 + a_1 - \dot{y}_d - \dot{\rho}_1 \sigma_1) = h_1, \quad (4a)$$

$$\dot{\sigma}_2 = (\rho_2)^{-1}(M^{-1}(x_1)(u - C(x_1, x_2)x_2 - g(x_1)) - \dot{a}_1 - \dot{\rho}_2 \sigma_2) = h_2. \quad (4b)$$

Define $\sigma = [\sigma_1^T, \sigma_2^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times n}$ and

$$\dot{\sigma} = h(\sigma, t) = [h_1^T, h_2^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times n}. \quad (5)$$

Moreover, let us define the open set $\Omega_\sigma = (-1, 1)^{2 \times n} \subset \mathbb{R}^{2 \times n}$. To prove Theorem 1, controller (3) should guarantee that the functions $T(\sigma_i)$, $i = 1, 2$ appearing in (3c) from (3j) and (3k) remain bounded. Owing to T being strictly increasing, it is adequate to prove that σ evolves strictly within a subset of Ω_σ for all $t \geq t_0$. Thus, all closed-loop signals σ_i , a_i , $i = 1, 2$ will remain bounded.

The proof of Theorem 1 consists of two lemmas, namely Lemma 1 and Lemma 2. The latter proves the boundedness of all closed-loop signals, while the former enforces prescribe performance characteristics for all $t \in [t_k, t_{k+1})$.

Lemma 1: Consider the nonlinear impulsive system (2) and Assumptions 1, 2. Given the predefined constants $\delta_{1,j}$ and τ satisfying $\delta_{1,j} > 0$, $0 < \tau < \bar{\tau}$, controller (3) guarantees that $|e_{1,j}(t)| < \delta_{1,j}$, for all $t \in [t_k + \tau, t_{k+1})$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $j = 1, \dots, n$.

Proof: There proof consists of three phases. In phase A, a unique solution $\sigma(t)$ of (5) is derived for a time interval $[t_0, \tau_{max})$, with $\tau_{max} \leq t_1$. Then, in phase B, we show that τ_{max} can be extended to t_1 and finally, in phase C, we extend the aforementioned results for all time intervals $[t_k, t_{k+1})$, $k \geq 2$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Phase A: The set Ω_σ is open and non-empty. Furthermore, owing to (3p), (3q), it guarantees that $\sigma(t_0) \in \Omega_\sigma$. Consequently, owing to the continuity of (5) with respect to t , it is concluded following standard theorems [24] that

exists a unique maximal solution of $\sigma(t)$ in $[t_0, \tau_{max})$, with $\tau_{max} \in [t_0, t_1]$.

Phase B: To proceed, owing to Phase A, we notice that ϵ_i and s_i , $i = 1, 2$ are well-defined for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Furthermore, let us define $P_i = \text{diag}([\frac{dT(\sigma_{i,1})}{d\sigma_{i,1}}, \dots, \frac{dT(\sigma_{i,n})}{d\sigma_{i,n}}]) > 0$, which is also well-defined owing to Phase A and its strictly increasing property. The rest of the analysis for Phase B follows a two step procedure.

Step 1: Define the positive definite function

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_1^T \epsilon_1. \quad (6)$$

Differentiating (6) with respect to time while using (4a), yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_1 &= \epsilon_1^T P_1(\rho_1)^{-1}(\rho_2 \sigma_2 + a_1 - \dot{y}_d - \dot{\rho}_1 \sigma_1) \\ &= \epsilon_1^T P_1(\rho_1)^{-1}(\rho_2 \sigma_2 - k_1 s_1 - k'_1 \epsilon_1 - \dot{y}_d - \dot{\rho}_1 \sigma_1), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Since $\sigma \in \Omega_\sigma$, we obtain that σ_1, σ_2 are bounded. Moreover, $\dot{\rho}_i, \rho_i, i = 1, 2$ are bounded by construction on $[t_0, \tau_{max})$ and $\rho_i > 0$. Also, \dot{y}_d is bounded owing to Assumption 1. Finally, let us define $E_1 = \|P_1(\rho_1)^{-1}(\rho_2 \sigma_2 - \dot{y}_d - \dot{\rho}_1 \sigma_1)\|$. Employing the Extreme Value Theorem on E_1 , we obtain the existence of a positive constant \bar{E}_1 such that $E_1 \leq \bar{E}_1$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Define $Q_i = P_i(\rho_i)^{-1} k_i > 0$ and $Q'_i = P_i(\rho_i)^{-1} k'_i > 0$. Thus, for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$:

$$\dot{V}_1 \leq -\epsilon_1^T Q_1 s_1 - \epsilon_1^T Q'_1 \epsilon_1 + \|\epsilon_1\| \bar{E}_1. \quad (8)$$

Utilizing $\epsilon_i^T s_i < \|\epsilon_i\|^4/n$, \dot{V}_1 becomes:

$$\dot{V}_1 \leq \bar{E}_1^2/4\lambda_{Q'_1} - \lambda_{Q_1} \|\epsilon_1\|^4/n, \quad (9)$$

where λ_A denotes the minimum eigenvalue of A , for a positive definite matrix A . Therefore, $\dot{V}_1 < 0$ when $\|\epsilon_1\| \geq \sqrt[4]{n\bar{E}_1^2/\lambda_{Q_1}\lambda_{Q'_1}}$. Thus, $\|\epsilon_1\| \leq \bar{\epsilon}_1 \triangleq \max\{\|\epsilon_1(t_0)\|, \sqrt[4]{n\bar{E}_1^2/\lambda_{Q_1}\lambda_{Q'_1}}\}$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Taking the inverse logarithmic function it yields:

$$-1 < T^{-1}(-\bar{\epsilon}_1) \leq \sigma_{1,j} \leq T^{-1}(\bar{\epsilon}_1) < 1. \quad (10)$$

for $j = 1, \dots, n$ and for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Furthermore, owing to the continuity of h_1 in (4a), and employing the Extreme Value Theorem, we obtain the existence of a positive constant \bar{h}_1 such that satisfy $\|h_1\| \leq \bar{h}_1$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Consequently, owing to (3c) $\|\dot{a}_1\|$ is bounded for all $[t_0, \tau_{max})$.

Step 2: Define the positive definite function

$$V_2 = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_2^T \epsilon_2. \quad (11)$$

Differentiating (11) with respect to time while using (4b), yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_2 &= \epsilon_2^T P_2(\rho_2)^{-1}(M^{-1}(x_1)(u - C(x_1, x_2)x_2 - g(x_1)) \\ &\quad - \dot{a}_1 - \dot{\rho}_2 \sigma_2) \\ &= \epsilon_2^T P_2(\rho_2)^{-1}(-M^{-1}(x_1)(C(x_1, x_2)x_2 + g(x_1)) - \dot{a}_1 \\ &\quad - M^{-1}(x_1)k_2 s_2 - M^{-1}(x_1)k'_2 \epsilon_2 - \dot{\rho}_2 \sigma_2) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Since $\sigma \in \Omega_\sigma$, we obtain that σ_2 is bounded. Additionally, $\dot{\rho}_i, \rho_i, i = 1, 2$ are bounded by construction on $[t_0, \tau_{max})$ and $\rho_i > 0$. Also, $|\dot{a}_1|$ is bounded for all $[t_0, \tau_{max})$ owing to Step 1. Finally, let us define $E_2 = \|P_2(\rho_2)^{-1}(-M^{-1}(x_1)(C(x_1, x_2)x_2 + g(x_1)) - \dot{a}_1 - \dot{\rho}_2 \sigma_2)\|$. Employing the Extreme Value Theorem on E_2 , we obtain the existence of a positive constant \bar{E}_2 such that $E_2 \leq \bar{E}_2$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Thus, for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_2 &\leq -\epsilon_2 Q_2 M^{-1}(x_1) s_2 - \epsilon_2 Q'_2 M^{-1}(x_1) \epsilon_2 + \|\epsilon_2\| \bar{E}_2 \\ &\leq \bar{E}_2^2/4\lambda_{Q'_2 M^{-1}} - \lambda_{Q_2 M^{-1}} \|\epsilon_2\|^4/n, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Thus, $\dot{V}_2 < 0$ when $\|\epsilon_2\| \geq \sqrt[4]{n\bar{E}_2^2/\lambda_{Q_2 M^{-1}}\lambda_{Q'_2 M^{-1}}}$, and consequently, for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$

$$\|\epsilon_2\| \leq \bar{\epsilon}_2 \triangleq \max\{\|\epsilon_2(t_0)\|, \sqrt[4]{n\bar{E}_2^2/\lambda_{Q_2 M^{-1}}\lambda_{Q'_2 M^{-1}}}\}. \quad (14)$$

Taking the inverse logarithmic function it yields:

$$-1 < T^{-1}(-\bar{\epsilon}_2) \leq \sigma_{2,j} \leq T^{-1}(\bar{\epsilon}_2) < 1. \quad (15)$$

Therefore, from (10) and (15) we obtain that σ evolves strictly with a compact subset of $\Omega'_\sigma \subset \Omega_\sigma$, where Ω'_σ depends on $\bar{E}_i, i = 1, 2$. As a result, states x_i , the intermediate signal a_1 and the control input $a_2 = u$ remain bounded for all $t \in [t_0, \tau_{max})$. Hence, using standard arguments [24], we extend τ_{max} to t_1 .

Phase C: To continue, we will prove that $\sigma(t_1^-) \in \Omega_\sigma$ implies that $\sigma(t_1) \in \Omega_\sigma$. In that direction, owing to $|\sigma_{i,j}(t_1^-)| < 1$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 1, \dots, n$, we obtain

$$-\rho_{i,j}(t_1^-) < x_{i,j}(t_1^-) - a_{i-1,j}(t_1^-) < \rho_{i,j}(t_1^-). \quad (16)$$

Using (2), (3g) and (3i), it yields

$$\begin{aligned} &-\rho_{i,j}(t_1) + \beta_{i,j}|\Delta x_{i,j}(1)| + \beta'_{i,j}|\Delta a_{i-1,j}(1)| \\ &< x_{i,j}(t_1) - \Delta x_{i,j}(1) - a_{i-1,j}(t_1) + \Delta a_{i-1,j}(1) \\ &< \rho_{i,j}(t_1) - \beta_{i,j}|\Delta x_{i,j}(1)| - \beta'_{i,j}|\Delta a_{i-1,j}(1)| \quad (17) \\ &-\rho_{i,j}(t_1) + \beta_{i,j}|\Delta x_{i,j}(1)| + \Delta x_{i,j}(1) + \beta'_{i,j}|\Delta a_{i-1,j}(1)| \\ &\quad - \Delta a_{i-1,j}(1) < x_{i,j}(t_1) - a_{i-1,j}(t_1) < \rho_{i,j}(t_1) \\ &-\beta_{i,j}|\Delta x_{i,j}(1)| + \Delta x_{i,j}(1) - \beta'_{i,j}|\Delta a_{i-1,j}(1)| \\ &\quad - \Delta a_{i-1,j}(1). \quad (18) \\ &-\rho_{i,j}(t_1) + (\beta_{i,j} - 1)|\Delta x_{i,j}(1)| + (\beta'_{i,j} - 1)|\Delta a_{i-1,j}(1)| \\ &< x_{i,j}(t_1) - a_{i-1,j}(t_1) < \rho_{i,j}(t_1) - (\beta_{i,j} - 1)|\Delta x_{i,j}(1)| \\ &\quad - (\beta'_{i,j} - 1)|\Delta a_{i-1,j}(1)| \quad (19) \end{aligned}$$

Since $\beta_{i,j}, \beta'_{i,j} > 1$, we obtain

$$-\rho_{i,j}(t_1) < x_{i,j}(t_1) - a_{i-1,j}(t_1) < \rho_{i,j}(t_1), \quad (20)$$

and $\sigma(t_1) \in \Omega_\sigma$.

The line of analysis of phases A,B,C can be repeated recursively for all time intervals $[t_k, t_{k-1})$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$, therefore proving Lemma 1.

To this point, we have proved that $\sigma(t)$ evolves strictly within Ω'_σ for all $t = [t_k, t_{k+1})$. However, owing to $\bar{E}_i, i = 1, 2$ which consecutively depends on the bounds of σ_i, ρ_i at

t_k , the size of Ω'_{σ_k} differ for each time interval. Therefore, to conclude the boundness of all signals in the closed-loop we have to show that these bounds are non-increasing with respect to k . The latter is achieved by proving that $V_1(t_k)$, $V_2(t_k)$ are upper bounded by constants independent of $V_1(t_{k-1})$, $V_2(t_{k-1})$.

Lemma 2: Consider the nonlinear impulsive system (2) and Assumptions 1, 2. Controller (3) guarantees the boundness of a_i, x_i and that $\sigma \in (-1, 1)^{2 \times n}$.

Proof: The proof of this lemma consists of 2 steps.

Step 1: From (9) we obtain:

$$\dot{V}_1 \leq \bar{E}_1^2 / 4\lambda_{Q_1'} - \lambda_{Q_1} \|\epsilon_1\|^4 / n, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1].$$

Consequently, there exist a constant $\lambda_{Q_1}/n > m_1 > 0$ such that

$$\dot{V}_1 \leq -m_1 \|\epsilon_1\|^4, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1].$$

provided that $\|\epsilon_1\| \geq \sqrt[4]{\bar{E}_1^2 / [4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\lambda_{Q_1}/n - m_1)]}$. Defining the constant $m_1' \triangleq m_1/4$ and utilizing the definition of V_1 , it yields:

$$\dot{V}_1 \leq -4m_1' V_1^2, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_1], \quad (21)$$

provided that $\|\epsilon_1\| \geq \sqrt[4]{\bar{E}_1^2 / [4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\lambda_{Q_1}/n - 4m_1')]}$. To proceed, we distinguish two cases.

Case 1 ($\|\epsilon_1\| \leq \sqrt[4]{\bar{E}_1^2 / [4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\lambda_{Q_1}/n - 4m_1')]}$): We proved that \dot{V}_1 is negative when $\|\epsilon_1\| \geq \sqrt[4]{\bar{E}_1^2 / [4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\lambda_{Q_1}/n - 4m_1')]}$. Hence, the upper bound of $\|\epsilon_1\|$ is $\sqrt[4]{\bar{E}_1^2 / [4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\lambda_{Q_1}/n - 4m_1')]}$ and the upper bound of V_1 is $\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\bar{E}_1^2 / [4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\lambda_{Q_1}/n - 4m_1')]}$ for all $t \in [t_0, t_1]$.

Case 2 ($\|\epsilon_1\| > \sqrt[4]{\bar{E}_1^2 / [4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\lambda_{Q_1}/n - 4m_1')]}$): exploiting the continuity of ϵ_1 , there exists a time constant $\hat{t}_1 \leq t_1$ such that $\|\epsilon_1\| > \sqrt[4]{\bar{E}_1^2 / [4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\lambda_{Q_1}/n - 4m_1')]} \quad \forall t \in [t_0, \hat{t}_1]$. Integrating (21), we obtain:

$$V_1 \leq \frac{V_1(t_0)}{4m_1' V_1(t_0)(t - t_0) + 1}, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, \hat{t}_1].$$

If $\hat{t}_1 < t_1$ then we apply the same analysis as in Case 1 $\forall t \in [\hat{t}_1, t_1]$. Consequently, aggregating both cases $\forall t \in [t_0, t_1]$, it yields

$$V_1(t) \leq \max \left\{ \frac{V_1(t_0)}{4m_1' V_1(t_0)(t - t_0) + 1}, \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\bar{E}_1^2}{4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\lambda_{Q_1}/n - 4m_1')}} \right\}. \quad (22)$$

Utilizing Assumption 2, we obtain

$$V_1(t_1^-) \leq \max \left\{ \frac{1}{4m_1' \bar{\tau}}, \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\bar{E}_1^2}{4\lambda_{Q_1'}(\frac{\lambda_{Q_1}}{n} - 4m_1')}} \right\} = \bar{V}_1 \quad (23)$$

Define $F_1(k)$ the energy injected to V_1 at $t \in \mathbb{J}$. Owing to Assumption 2, we have that $F_1(k)$ is bounded for all $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$. Therefore, $V_1(t_1) = V_1(t_1^-) + F_1(1) \leq \bar{V}_1 + F_1(1)$. Hence,

$$V_1(t) \leq \max \{V_1(t_0), V_1(t_1^-) + F_1(1)\}. \quad (24)$$

Therefore by induction, we have for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k \geq 2$

$$V_1(t_k) = V_1(t_k^-) + F_1(k) \leq \bar{V}_1 + F_1(k), \quad (25)$$

and for all $t \in [t_{k-1}, t_k]$

$$V_1(t) \leq \max \{\bar{V}_1 + F_1(k-1), \bar{V}_1 + F_1(k)\}. \quad (26)$$

Aggregating all time intervals, we obtain

$$V_1(t) \leq \max \{V_1(t_0), \bar{V}_1 + F_1(1), \dots, \bar{V}_1 + F_1(k)\}, \quad \forall t \geq t_0. \quad (27)$$

To proceed, notice that $V_1(t)$ and \bar{V}_1 are bounded independently on k . Since $F_1(k)$ is bounded, we conclude that $V_1(t)$ is bounded $\forall t \in [t_0, \infty)$. Therefore, we have proved that $\epsilon_1(t)$ and $a_1(t)$ remain bounded $\forall t \in [t_0, \infty)$. Furthermore, let ζ_1 denotes the bound of $\|\epsilon_1(t)\|$. Hence, it holds for all $t \in [t_0, \infty)$

$$-1 < T^{-1}(-\zeta_1) \leq \sigma_1(t) \leq T^{-1}(\zeta_1) < 1, \quad (28)$$

which concludes that $x_1(t)$ remains bounded, and owing to (3h), $\rho_1(t)$ is also bounded.

Step 2: We follow the same line of analysis as in step 1 obtaining that $V_2(t)$ remains bounded for all $t \in [t_0, \infty)$. Thus, $x_2(t)$, $\epsilon_2(t)$, $\rho_2(t)$ and $u = a_2(t)$ are bounded for all $t \in [t_0, \infty)$, concluding the proof of Lemma 2 and consequently of Theorem 1.

V. SIMULATION

To illustrate the performance of our proposed controller, we demonstrate simulations performed on a planar two-link robotic manipulator with parameters as considered in [25]. The first state is $x_1 = [q_1, q_2]^T$, where q_1, q_2 (rad) are the angle positions of joints 1 and 2 constrained within $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$. The second state is $x_2 = [\dot{q}_1, \dot{q}_2]^T$, where \dot{q}_1, \dot{q}_2 (rad/s) are the respective angular velocities constrained within $[-2\pi, 2\pi]$. Initially, the robot is at rest at $x_1(0) = [\frac{65\pi}{180}, \frac{65\pi}{180}]$. The desired trajectories to be tracked are $y_{d,1}(t) = \pi/9 - (\pi/9)\sin(\pi t/4)$ and $y_{d,2}(t) = \pi/2 - \pi/9 - (\pi/9)\cos(\pi t/4)$. If a joint reaches its limit, then the respective angular velocity becomes equal to zero and the joint position is moved away from its limit by $\pi/360$ rad, thus an impulsive phenomenon occurs. For both output tracking errors $e_{1,j}$, $j = 1, 2$, the requirement is to converge to the set $\{e_{1,j} \in \mathbb{R} : |e_{1,j}(t)| \leq 5\pi/180\}$ no later than the fixed time $\tau = 2s$. We set $\delta_{1,j} = 5\pi/180$, $j = 1, 2$ and we implement the proposed controller with control elements as dictated in Theorem 1. In addition, to achieve reasonable control effort with smooth state evolution we chose $k_{1,j} = 0.5$, $k'_{1,j} = 1$, $k_{2,j} = 0.15$, $k'_{2,j} = 2$, $\beta_{1,j} = 1.5$, $\beta_{2,j} = 2.5$, $\beta'_{2,j} = 2.5$ and $\delta_{2,j} = 20\pi/180$, $j = 1, 2$. The prescribed performance functions are selected, at $t_0 = 0$, as $\rho_{1,1} = (90.5e^{-1.8997t} + 3)\pi/180$, $\rho_{1,2} = (30.5e^{-1.3218t} + 3)\pi/180$, $\rho_{2,1} = (205e^{-1.3049t} + 5)\pi/180$

Fig. 1. Evolution of angular position q_j and angular velocity \dot{q}_j alongside their constraints for $j = 1, 2$.

and $\rho_{2,2} = (200e^{-1.2917t} + 5)\pi/180$, where $\lambda_{i,j}^0$ satisfy (3p) for $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 1, 2$.

The performance of the aforementioned control scheme is illustrated in Figs. 1-3. In Fig. 1, state evolution is presented alongside the corresponding constraints. Apparently, the system is subject to impulses, satisfying $t_1 - t_0 = \bar{\tau} = 4s > \tau = 2s$ and $t_{k+2} - t_{k+1} = 8 > \tau$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$. The output errors $e_{1,j}$ and the intermediate errors $e_{2,j} = x_{2,j} - a_{1,j}$ are pictured in Fig. 2 and the requested control inputs are presented in Fig. 3. Clearly, the required performance is achieved with bounded control effort, regardless the presence of impulsive phenomena.

VI. CONCLUSION

We considered the problem of controlling uncertain Euler-Lagrange systems in the presence of aperiodic impulses affecting the system state. Following the prescribe performance methodology, we designed a state feedback controller capable of guaranteeing that the output tracking error will converge to a neighborhood of zero of pre-selected size, in no greater than a prespecified fixed time. In addition, all closed-loop signals remained bounded. Simulations results exemplify and verify the theoretical findings.

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Fig. 2. Evolution of the output tracking errors $e_{1,j} = x_{1,j} - y_{d,j}$ and the intermediate errors $e_{2,j} = x_{2,j} - a_{1,j}$ alongside with their corresponding performance bounds for $j = 1, 2$.

Fig. 3. The requested control inputs u_j for $j = 1, 2$.

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